

FIRM CHARACTERISTICS AND PROFITABILITY IN NIGERIAN INDUSTRIAL GOODS FIRMS: ASSESSING THE MODERATING EFFECT OF BOARD INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract

The study examined the firm characteristics and profitability of Nigerian industrial goods industries, with the moderating effect of board independence. Firm size, liquidity, and leverage were used as proxies for firm characteristics, while return on assets was used as a measure of profitability. Ten industrial goods firms were sampled from 2014 to 2023, using annual accounts and an ex post facto research design was adopted. The collected data were analysed using Generalised Least Squares. The finding shows that firm size has a positive and significant effect on profitability. In contrast, liquidity and leverage showed a positive, insignificant effect and a negative, insignificant impact on return on assets, respectively. In assessing the moderating effect of board independence, the study found that it does not moderate the interaction among firm size, liquidity, and leverage on profitability. The study concluded that the moderating effect of board independence does not significantly interact with firm characteristics to affect the profitability of industrial firms in Nigeria. To improve their profitability, the study recommended that industrial goods firms should seek strategic firm size expansion, have a modest total debt-to-total assets ratio, and invest liquid assets wisely.

Keywords: Firm Characteristics, Profitability, Board Independence, Industrial Goods Firm.

INTRODUCTION

The industrial goods sector is a crucial catalyst for economic development in Nigeria, improving living standards and driving growth (Ugbomhe & Omoaka, 2025; Barigbon & Idoniboye-Obu, 2022).

A firm's performance is shaped by its internal qualities, known as firm characteristics—such as size, leverage, and liquidity—which are distinct from external economic factors and influence a company's strategic decisions and success (Akenroye et al., 2022; Mbonu & Amahalu, 2021). Improving profitability requires effectively leveraging these characteristics.

Although board independence is a recognised mechanism to reduce agency problems (Sharifah et al. 2016), and prior studies have employed it as a moderating variable in various contexts (e.g., Abdulkarim & Bahamman, 2021; El-Feky & Baroma, 2024), its specific role in the relationship between firm characteristics and profitability in the industrial goods sector remains unexamined. To address inconsistent findings in this relationship, a moderator is recommended (Soderund 2023; Lai, 2013). This study, therefore, aims to fill this gap by examining the moderating effect of board independence on the relationships between firm size, liquidity, leverage, and profitability (ROA) in Nigerian industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Also previous studies have not examined the moderating effect of board independence within the period of 2014-2023.

LITERATURE REVIEW

a) Conceptual Framework

The study looks at how company attributes, including size, liquidity, and leverage, affect profitability as measured by return on assets (ROA). It also examined how the relationship between the firm's characteristics and ROA is influenced by board independence. Therefore, independent boards can enhance governance and reduce agency conflicts, both of which impact profitability. This is diagrammatically represented below:

Fig 2.1: The framework of the study. (Adapted from Sulaiman and Khalid (2024))

PROFITABILITY

Profitability is the primary measure of a firm's financial performance, indicating management effectiveness, business efficiency, and organisational health (Chabachib et al., 2020; Yusufu et al., 2023). It reflects an entity's ability to generate profit from its expenses and investments

(Arize, 2023) and is crucial for meeting stakeholder commitments and ensuring long-term sustainability (Pamungkas et al., 2017). Firm characteristics, which are internal attributes under management's control, are key factors in explaining differences in profitability across organisations (Jibril & Idris, 2022). Profitability is commonly measured by metrics like Return on Assets (ROA), which indicates how efficiently management uses resources to generate profit (Oyedokun, 2019). Despite various studies on firm characteristics and profitability, the moderating role of board independence in this relationship has received insufficient attention.

FIRM CHARACTERISTICS

a) Firm Size

Firm size is the scale of a company's operation and is influenced by factors such as market capitalisation, employment numbers, asset values, and sales volume. Firm classification as large or small depends on its total assets or total sales generated (Ezekwesili & Ezejiolor, 2022). Sulaiman and Khalid (2024) argued that large firms have more human capital, enabling them to introduce products to the market more quickly than smaller companies. Firm size is important for investment decisions, as the economies-of-scale theory suggests that larger firms benefit from cost savings and higher marginal productivity (Abdulrahman et al., 2021). Abbasi and Malik (2015) found that larger firms often develop bureaucracy, and their size can become a disadvantage once they reach a large scale. Arize (2023), however, posited that it is important to remember that larger companies are more susceptible to agency problems due to conflicting interests and the potential for corporate failure. The study measured firm size using the natural logarithm of total assets.

b) Liquidity

Liquidity refers to cash and cash equivalents, measured as the amount of assets that can be quickly converted into cash without sacrificing value to cover short-term liabilities. Cash and bank balances, marketable securities, and receivables are mainly referred to as liquidity assets. Liquidity impacts an entity's financial position, directly influencing its ability to generate profit. Chabachib et al. (2020) indicated that investors tend to focus more on companies with strong liquidity. Liquidity is a business's capability to settle maturing financial obligations, especially short-term debts. As a vital factor, it enables a firm to meet its short-term commitments, and its consistent availability can be maintained through profitable projects (Efuntade & Akinola, 2020).

c) Leverage

Leverage is a financing method that involves borrowing money to achieve a return higher than the cost of that borrowing. According to Ahmed et al. (2025), an independent board with a clear approach to sourcing leverage can avoid excessive debt that may lead to financial risk, which refers to the possibility of incurring adverse financial costs, and may result in revenue or capital loss (Anastasiia et al., 2021). As Ojo (2012) states, a firm's risk and financial leverage increase as its debt proportion rises. Kaguri (2013) suggested that a higher debt level can reduce agency costs, address inefficiencies, and boost a firm's profitability. According to Jensen and Meckling

(1976), the use of high leverage can motivate agents to invest in profitable ventures that generate returns for owners, as failure to pay interest might lead to the company's liquidation and risk managers' jobs. One common way to measure leverage is the debt-to-equity ratio, which indicates the proportion of the firm's capital that is financed by debt versus equity.

BOARD INDEPENDENCE

Board independence, defined as the proportion of non-executive directors without material ties to the company (Ahmed et al., 2025), is crucial for impartial oversight and reducing agency problems (Achema et al., 2022). While theoretically linked to long-term success (Yusufu et al., 2023), its empirical relationship with profitability is mixed. Some studies, such as Silaban et al. (2025) in Indonesia and Monther et al. (2022) in Malaysia, find a positive impact on performance. However, research in Nigeria by Ebire et al. (2024) and Habib & Saleh (2021) specifically found that board independence had an insignificant effect, and even a negative insignificant effect as a moderator, indicating conflicting evidence on its direct financial benefits.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Agency Theory, prominently established by Jensen and Meckling (1976), examines the conflicts that arise when principals (owners) hire agents (managers) to act on their behalf, a relationship often plagued by asymmetric information and moral hazard (Tuttle et al., 1997). To mitigate these problems, strategies such as board independence are employed to provide oversight and control (Dalton et al., 2007), with a core assumption that this improves financial performance (Tarazi, 2019). This study applies Agency Theory, focusing on how independent directors can monitor managers and support profitable decision-making.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Effect of Firm Size on Profitability

Various studies have explored the relationship between firm size and profitability. The research by Isik et al. (2017) examined the impact of firm size on profitability in the Turkish manufacturing sector using a dynamic panel data approach. The study accounted for several variables and found that firm size, measured by the firm's assets, turnover, and number of employees, had a positive influence on profitability, as indicated by return on assets. The study concluded that regardless of how business size is measured, their empirical findings show that the effect of firm size on profitability remains consistent. Similarly, Nkasi and Mide (2025) conducted empirical research on how firm size and liquidity affect the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study covered the period from 2015 to 2023. Using a fixed-effects regression model, the study found that size had a positive and significant effect on ROA, indicating operational efficiencies and a larger market for bigger firms. Abdul-Khadir et al. (2023) analysed data from 13 quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria, assessing the effect of firm size and age on Return on Assets (ROA) from 2013 to 2022. They used regression analysis to examine the potential impact of size and age on ROA. The results showed that firm

size had a non-significant effect on ROA, while age showed a different result. Consequently, the study suggested that management in this sector should focus more on experience and longevity to boost profitability (ROA) rather than firm size. Following the above uncertainties, we formulate the following hypothesis:

H₀₁: Firm size has no significant effect on the profitability of listed Industrial Goods Firms in Nigeria.

Effect of Liquidity on Profitability

The relationship between liquidity and profitability has been explored in various literature. The study by Asemota et al. (2023) examined the impact of liquidity management on the profitability of industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2015 to 2020, focusing on 10 listed companies. The independent variable, liquidity, was measured by the current ratio, while the dependent variable, profitability, was represented by return on assets. The study used the least squares regression method to analyze the data and found that liquidity has a negative and insignificant effect on profitability (ROA), aligning with the trade-off theory referenced in their research. Based on these findings, the study recommends maintaining an optimal level of liquidity to boost profitability. Khan & Siddiqui (2023) investigated three key features that influence performance in selected industries in Pakistan. The independent variables included liquidity, leverage, and supply chain finance, while the dependent variable was performance. Their data spanned ten years from 2011 to 2020, and they employed the generalised method of moments (GMM) for analysis. The results showed that these three variables had a positive effect on performance across the cement, textile, sugar, and pharmaceutical sectors in Pakistan. Kartiningsih & Daryanto (2020) conducted a study in Indonesia's food and beverage industry on how certain firm characteristics impact profitability. Using secondary data and multiple linear regression analysis to test their hypotheses, the results revealed that liquidity, age, size, and leverage all had a positive and significant effect on profitability. The study recommended that the sector should efficiently pool its resources and debts to generate higher profits.

H₀₂: Liquidity has no significant effect on the profitability of listed Industrial Goods Firms in Nigeria

Effect of Leverage on Profitability

Some studies have attributed leverage to profitability. The research by Arhinful and Radmehr (2023) on Japan-selected industries found that interest coverage, cash coverage, and service obligations of debts (proxied by leverage) had various effects on financial performance, as measured by ROA, Tobin's Q, and ROE. The results revealed that interest coverage and cash coverage had a positive influence on performance, while debt service negatively impacts it. The research by Eneh et al. (2024) examined firm attributes and the financial performance of industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. Data analysis using multiple regression showed that size has a positive and significant relationship with performance, whereas liquidity and leverage have negative relationships. The study suggests management in this sector should aim to balance liquidity and leverage optimally to enhance profitability. Wisam (2024) studied the effect of leverage on profitability in selected Jordanian companies

listed on the Amman Stock Exchange from 2019 to 2022. Leverage was defined as the total liabilities used to finance the company's assets. The study utilised E-Views 10 to test the hypotheses. The key conclusion was that leverage has an inverse relationship with profitability among the sampled companies, and it recommends adopting methods to adjust the proportion of liabilities to assets to improve company profitability.

H₀₃: Leverage has no significant effect on the profitability of listed Industrial Goods Firms in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The ex post facto research design was employed in this study, which is quantitative in nature. This study analysed secondary data on firm attributes, size, liquidity, leverage, and profitability (Return on Assets) in listed industrial firms in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. The sample includes the 10 industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 31, 2023. Due to data availability, a non-probability purposive sampling method was employed, as only ten (10) firms have complete data for the period of 2014-2023. The data analysis was performed using Stata 14 Statistical Software. Multiple regression analysis techniques were then utilised to test the hypotheses and draw conclusions from the equation of the model, as provided below:

Model

Model 1:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_2 LQD_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq.1}$$

Model 2: The application of the moderating variable

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_2 LQD_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \beta_4 FSIZE_{it} * BIND_{it} + \beta_5 LQD_{it} * BIND_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{it} * BIND_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq.2}$$

Where:

- ROA = Return on Assets
- FSIZE = Firm Size
- LQD = Liquidity
- LEV = Leverage
- BIND = Board Independence
- β_0 = The constant to be estimated
- $\beta_1 - \beta_6$ = The coefficient of the estimate
- ϵ = The error term
- t = Period
- i = Firm

Explained below are the variables used in this study, which were adopted from earlier research and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Variable Measurement and Justification

Variables	Type	Measurement	Justification
Return on Assets	Dependent	Profit After Tax/Total Assets	Yusuf et al. (2023) Gara et al (2025)
Firm Size	Independent	Natural Logarithm of a firm's Total Assets.	Yusuf et al.(2023) Sulaiman and Khalid (2024).
Liquidity	Independent	Current Assets to Liabilities due within 1 year (Current Liabilities)	Eneh et al. (2024). Talatu et al. (2024)
Leverage	Independent	Total Debt to Total Assets	Khan and Siddiqui (2023) Eneh et al. (2024).
Board Independence	Moderating	The proportion of independent directors relative to the total members of the board.	Ahmed et al. (2025) Shamsul et al.(2022)

Source: Researcher's compilation (2025)

Table 1 presents a description of the various variables and their measurement. The justifications for these variables are supported by different authors, as indicated in the table above.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum	Obs.
ROA	6.623	14.205	-58.01	53.96	100
FSIZE	15.578	3.681	6.82	22.09	100
LQD	9.440	22.695	0.19	113.17	100
LEV	102.358	258.742	-391.65	1855.65	100
BIND	75.906	15.697	0	100	100
FSIZEBIN	1206.844	418.523	0	1914.82	100
LQDBIND	572.015	1262.827	0	6408.04	100
LEVBIND	6801.666	14512.03	-26111.28	111339.2	100

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025 (STATA 14)

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the data collected for each variable under investigation. As shown above, the mean value for return on industrial good firms is 6.623%. A standard deviation for return on assets is 14.21%, with a minimum of -58.01% and a maximum of 53.96% indicating profitable firms. The average value for firm size is 15.58 billion, with a standard deviation of 3.68 billion, indicating low variability in firm size. Liquidity has a mean of 9.44 billion, a standard deviation of 22.695, a minimum of 0.19 billion, and a maximum of 113.17 billion, indicating high disparity in liquidity within the industry. Leverage has a mean of 102.36 billion, a standard deviation of 258.74 billion, with a minimum of -391.65 billion and a maximum of 1855.65 billion, suggesting a high volume of debt. Board independence has a mean of 75.91% with a standard deviation of approximately 16% and a maximum of 100%. This indicates that all industrial goods firms have an independent board. The interaction between firm size and board independence has a calculated mean of 1206.84 billion, a standard deviation of 418.52 billion, and a maximum of 1914.82 billion.

The mean, standard deviation, and maximum values of the interaction between board independence and liquidity are 572.015, 1262.827, and 6408.40, respectively. With a mean of 6,801.67 and a standard deviation of 14,512.03, the relationship between board independence and leverage ranges from -2,611.26 to 111,339.2. The wider disparity between the means and the standard deviations suggests a high inequality among the firms.

Table 3: Normality Test

Variable	W	V	Z	Prob.
ROA	0.875	10.281	5.169	0.000
FSIZE	0.865	11.087	5.337	0.000
LQD	0.426	47.317	8.556	0.000
LEV	0.376	51.443	8.741	0.000
BIND	0.790	17.262	6.319	0.000
FSIZEBIND	0.790	5.154	3.638	0.000
LQDBIND	0.459	44.640	8.427	0.000
LEVBIND	0.413	48.394	8.606	0.000

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025 (STATA 14)

Table 3 above exposes the normality test for the dependent variable, independent variables, moderating variable, and interaction between the independent variables and moderating variable using the Shapiro-Wilk test.

The table reveals that all variables (return on assets, firm size, liquidity, leverage, board independence, and interactions of board independence with all the independent variables) have a probability value of 0.000, which indicates that the variables are not normally distributed. Hence, Spearman's rank correlation is most appropriate for the correlation matrix.

Table 4: Correlation matrix (Spearman's rank Correlation)

Variable	ROA	FSIZE	LQD	LEV	BIND	FSIZEBIND	LQDBIND	LEVBIND
ROA	1.000							
FSIZE	0.5416	1.000						
LQD	-0.3465	-0.6806	1.000					
LEV	-0.3475	-0.3689	0.0749	1.000				
BIND	0.1831	0.4387	-0.3993	-0.2456	1.000			

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025 (STATA 14)

Table 4 denotes the correlation between the variables in this study. Based on the outcomes, there is an interrelationship between the dependent variable, the independent variables, and the moderating variable, and no indication of multicollinearity.

The table illustrates a positive relationship between return on assets and firm size and board independence, suggesting that an increase in these variables is likely to result in growth in profitability. This suggests that industrial goods firms need size and board independence to boost profitability.

Table 5: Panel Regression Analysis (Generalised Least Squares)

Model I Generalised Least Squares				Model II Generalised Least Squares		
Variable	Cof.	Z	Prob.	Cof.	Z	Prob.
FSIZE	1.528	3.15	0.002	2.018	2.42	0.015
LQD	0.805	0.90	0.367	-0.501	-0.85	0.394
LEV	-0.013	-2.02	0.028	0.120	2.14	0.032
FSIZEBIND				-0.004	-0.62	0.533
LQDBIND				0.09	0.88	0.380
LEVBIND				-0.002	-2.40	0.016
Wald Test						
Chiz			26.68			35.65
Prob.			0.000			0.000
vif			2.06			86.34
Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity						
Chiz			15.14			10.21
Prob.			0.000			0.001
Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects						
Chiz			-68.97			73.04
Prob.			0.000			0.000
Hausman Test						
Chiz			3.08			73.04
Prob.			0.004			0.000
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data:						
F. Stat.			0.142			0.039
Prob.			0.715			0.8474
Pesaran's test of cross-sectional independence:						
F. Stat.			2.452			2.612
Prob.			0.014			0.009

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025 (STATA 14)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Hausman test and its confirmatory tests (Testparm or Langrangian Multiplier test) were conducted to determine the best estimating technique among Random effect, Fixed Effect, and Pooled OLS. The null hypothesis of the Hausman test is that the preferred model is the fixed effects model. The probability of the result for model 1 ($p = 0.004$) and model II (0.00) suggests that the null hypothesis is to be rejected. Thus, the preferred estimation method is the fixed effects model. The probability value of the confirmatory test (LM Test), which is 0.000 for model I and 0.000 for model II, supports the result of the Hausman test and suggests that Random-Effect Regression is not the best estimating technique for either model; hence, the models were regressed using the Fixed-Effect Model estimation.

Diagnostic tests were conducted to assess the suitability of the model; specifically, a heteroskedasticity test was performed to examine variations in the model's residuals. The probability value for the heteroskedasticity test result was 0.000 for model I, while that of model II is 0.001. This implies that the model is heteroskedastic, meaning that the variance is not constant over time. Thus, the study rejects the null hypothesis. Also, the models' coefficients and residuals were checked for an autocorrelation problem using the Wooldridge test, and the probability value of 0.715 for model I and 0.8474 for model II, which revealed that the coefficients and the residuals of the model are not correlated and thus, there is no presence of serial correlation problem in the model. Furthermore, the model's coefficients and residuals were checked for cross cross-sectional independence problem using Pesaran's test of cross-sectional independence, as well as with the probability value of 0.014 for model I and 0.009 for model II, it revealed that the coefficients and the residual of the models have cross sectional independence problem and thus, there is presence of cross-sectional independence problem in the two models. The econometric issues of heteroscedasticity and cross-sectional dependency observed in the model were addressed by running the generalised least squares regression.

The generalised least squares regression for Model I in Table 5 reveals that firm size has a positive and significant effect on return on assets, indicating that a one-unit increase in firm size can lead to a rise in return on assets. Liquidity has a positive and insignificant effect on return on assets, while leverage has a negative and significant impact on return on assets. This implies that a unit increase in leverage will result in a decrease in the value of return on assets of industrial goods for the period under investigation.

Furthermore, Model II shows the moderating effect of board independence on the interaction between firm size, liquidity, and leverage with return on assets. The moderating effect of board independence on the interaction between return on assets and firm size has a negative coefficient of -0.004 and an insignificant p-value of 0.5333. Model I, which does not account for the moderating effect of board independence, has a positive coefficient (1.528) and a significant effect ($p = 0.002$). This implies that board independence does not moderate the interaction between return on assets and firm size; hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Moreover, the moderating effect of board independence on the interaction between liquidity and return on assets shows that there is positive (0.09) and insignificant (0.380) compared to the interaction of liquidity and return on assets without the moderating variable in model I shows a positive (0.805) an insignificant (0,367), which implies that board independence does not moderates the interaction of liquidity on return on assets. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Finally, the moderating effect of board independence on the interaction between leverage and return on assets has negative (-0.002) and significant effect (0.016), in the same vein, the result of interaction of leverage and return on assets without the moderating effect of board independence shows a negative (-0.013) and significant (0.028), this implies that board independent does not moderate the interaction between leverage and return on assets. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The result of the Wald test, which measured the magnitude of change caused on return on assets by the combination of the interactions of independent variables and the moderating effect of board independence for model II, suggests that approximately 27% of the variation in return on assets is caused by the joint interaction of the independent variables and moderating effect of board independence considered (firm size, liquidity and leverage), about 73% of the variation in return on assets can be traced to all other factors that also influence return on assets, but not considered in this model I.

Observations

1) Effect of firm size and profitability

This study examines firms' characteristics and profitability in Nigerian industrial goods firms, assessing the moderating effect of board independence. The findings suggest that firm size has a positive and significant impact on profitability (Cof. = 1.528; $p = 0.002$). This result confirms the rejection of the null hypothesis, which is consistent with the study by Nkasi and Mide (2025), which found that firm size has a positive and significant effect on ROA, indicating operational efficiencies and a larger market for larger firms. However, this result contradicts the research work of Abdul-Khadir et al. (2023), which found that firm size, as an indicator of excessive assets, has no significant effect on ROA.

2) Effect of liquidity and profitability

The study found that liquidity has a positive and statistically insignificant effect on profitability (Cof. = 0.805; $p = 0.367$). This finding aligned with the result of Asemota et al. (2023), which supports the optimal level of liquidity to boost profitability. Nevertheless, the results contradict the study of Karhningsih and Daryanto (2020), who found a positive and significant effect of liquidity on profitability.

3) Effect of leverage and profitability

Leverage reveals a negative and insignificant effect on return on assets (Cof. = -0.013; $p = 0.20$). This regression analysis suggests that a unit increase in leverage hurts profitability, supporting the null hypothesis that leverage has no noticeable effect on profitability. The findings of Wisam (2024) confirm this conclusion, although it runs counter to those of Arhinful and Radnehr (2023), who discovered that debt had a favourable effect on profitability.

4) Moderating Effects of Board Independence

The Board's independence and Firm size

The study observes that the moderating effect of board independence and firm size on profitability is presented as negative and insignificant (Cof. = -0.004, $p = 0.533$). Before the introduction of moderation, firm size exhibited a significant effect ($p = 0.002$) on return on assets; after the introduction, firm size showed an insignificant impact ($p = 0.533$) on return on assets. This signifies that an increase in board independence tends to decrease profitability.

The Board Independence and Liquidity

The study revealed that the moderating effect of board independence and liquidity has a positive but insignificant (Cof. = 0.09, $p = 0.380$) impact on return on assets, suggesting that higher liquidity tends to offset the profitability of industrial goods firms.

The Board's independence and Leverage

Board independence reduced the association between leverage and profitability, resulting in a negative and negligible effect (Cof. = -0.0002, $p = 0.016$). This indicates that leverage will reduce profitability due to poor debt management.

CONCLUSION, SUMMARY, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examines the composite relationships between a firm's size, liquidity, and leverage and its profitability, with board independence serving as a moderating factor. The findings, which provide valuable insights, are grouped into two main classes. The study shows that firm size has a positive and significant impact on profitability (return on assets), while liquidity has a positive but statistically insignificant effect, and leverage has a negative but negligible impact on profitability. Additionally, the study finds that board independence does not moderate the relationship between firm size and profitability of industrial firms in Nigeria. Similarly, the study reveals that board independence does not moderate the link between liquidity and leverage on profitability. Overall, the study concludes that the moderating role of board independence does not affect how firm characteristics affect profitability in Nigerian industrial firms.

Based on the results, the study recommends that the Management of industrial goods firms should seek strategic firm size expansion, as the interactive effect of firm size does not result in growth of profitability. The study further recommended that a modest total debt-to-total assets ratio will enhance profitability. Furthermore, the liquid assets should be invested wisely to increase the profitability of the firm's industrial goods in Nigeria.

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The authors confirmed that all work is original and developed from the research effort of the researchers. All references are appropriately acknowledged, using the APA style.

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